

Kinetics and mechanism of the reaction of hydroxopentaaquarhodium(III) ion with picolinic acid in aqueous media

S. Mohanty^a, S. Anand^a and P. Mohanty^{b*}

^aRegional Research Laboratory, ^bDepartment of Chemistry, Utkal University, Vanivihar, Bhubaneswar-751 004, India

E-mail : mohantyprakash@hotmail.com Fax : 91-0674-581637

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The kinetics of the reaction of picolinic acid (HL⁺) with hydroxopentaaquarhodium(III) have been studied over the range $2.58 \leq 10^3 [\text{HL}^+] \leq 12.90$, $3.68 \leq \text{pH} \leq 4.3$, $45^\circ \leq t \leq 65^\circ$ and $I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (NaClO₄). The reaction takes place via an outer-sphere association between RhOH²⁺ and HL (conjugate base of HL⁺) followed by transformation of the outer into an inner sphere complex (chelate is formed) by slow interchange. The anation rate constant (k_{an}) of RhOH²⁺ at 25° and $I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (NaClO₄) is estimated to be $2.34 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$. ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger for k_{an} path are evaluated. Anation reaction of RhOH²⁺ follows an I_a path.

Enzymatic reactions under biological conditions are activated or controlled by metallic cations, which are in a combined state with proteins, amino acids, lipids and related compounds. Studies of metal complex formation with various biomolecules are important because they act as models for complicated proteins¹. Reactions of picolinic acid with metal ions are of recent interest².

Among the platinum family elements, rhodium is highly significant due to its wide application³ and the diverse type of mechanism exhibited during anation reaction. In order to examine the mechanistic aspect of Rh(OH₂)₆³⁺, we have studied the reaction of Rh^{III} with L-aspartic acid⁴ and ferricyanide ion⁵ in aqueous medium. Here, the interaction of picolinic acid with hydroxopentaaquarhodium(III) is reported.

Results and discussion

Effect of Rh^{III} concentration on reaction rate : In the first set of kinetic experiments, the Rh^{III} concentration was varied at fixed picolinic acid concentration of $7.74 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. The ionic strength, pH and temperature were kept constant. The pseudo-first order plots were linear ($r = 0.99$) in each case, giving $k_{\text{obs}} = (5.58 \pm 0.3) \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and showing that the reaction is first order in $[\text{Rh}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}}$, ($T = \text{total}$). The independence of k_{obs} at 55° under the condition $[\text{HL}^+]_{\text{T}} = 7.74 \times 10^{-3}$, $I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $\text{pH} \approx 4.3$ over a $[\text{Rh}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}}$ range from 2.58×10^{-4} to $5.16 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, is in agreement with first order dependence on $[\text{Rh}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}}$. The rate law therefore, is given by eqn. (1),

$$\text{Rate} = -d[\text{Rh}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}}/dt = k_{\text{obs}}[\text{Rh}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}} \quad (1)$$

Effect of pH on reaction rate : Under the conditions $t = 55^\circ$, $[\text{Rh}^{\text{III}}] = 2.58 \times 10^{-4}$, $[\text{HL}^+]_{\text{T}} = 7.74 \times 10^{-3}$ and $I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (NaClO₄), pH changed from 3.68 to 4.30, the $10^5 k_{\text{obs}}$ values were found to increase from 3.39 to 5.30 s⁻¹. At pHs 3.68, 3.90, 4.11, 4.25 and 4.30, the values of $10^5 k_{\text{obs}}$ are 3.39, 3.70, 4.50, 4.91 and 5.30 s⁻¹. The increase in k_{obs} due to increase in pH may be due to increase in the concentration of RhOH²⁺. Dissociation of $[\text{Rh}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+}$ takes place as given in eqn. (2),

The $\text{p}K_h$ value⁶ of $[\text{Rh}(\text{OH}_2)_6]^{3+}$ is 3.3 at 25°. Thus with increase in pH the percentage of more labile hydroxopentaaquarhodium(III) species in solution is increased. The presence of OH⁻ ligand in the hydroxo aqua species in several cases increased lability (due to π bonding) and therefore increased rates are found with Co^{III}⁷, Al^{III}⁸, Ga^{III}⁹, Mn^{III}¹⁰, Fe^{III}¹¹, Cr^{III}¹² or Rh^{III}¹³. The hydroxide ligand increases the water exchange rate constant of $[\text{Rh}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5\text{OH}]^{2+}$ relative to $[\text{Rh}(\text{OH}_2)_6]^{3+}$. Picolinic acid also participates in the acid-base reaction equilibria. By increasing pH of the medium, the concentration of the conjugate base from HL⁺ increases. $\text{p}K_1$ and $\text{p}K_2$ of picolinic acid¹⁴ are 1.03 and 5.21, respectively.

At lower pH (3.68), the HL form will predominate as

the pH is increased from 3.68 to 4.3, the concentration of L^- will also increase. If L^- would have participated in the reaction, the reaction should have shown second order inverse dependence in $[H^+]$. Hence, the active species involved in the anation reaction is probably HL. Thus the effect of pH can be explained by eqn. (3),

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k_1 + k_2 K_h [H^+]^{-1} \quad (3)$$

here k_1 and k_2 are the observed rate constants when $[Rh(OH_2)_6]^{3+}$ and $[Rh(OH_2)_5OH]^{2+}$ are the reacting species, respectively. The plot of k_{obs} (55°) vs $[H^+]^{-1}$ was linear with intercept = 2.77×10^{-5} and slope = 1.25×10^{-9} . The correlation coefficient was found to be 0.994.

Effect of $[HL^+]$ on reaction rate : The effect of varying $[HL^+]_T$ on the reaction rate was studied at fixed $[H^+]$ and between 45 and 65°. At fixed $[Rh^{III}]_T = 2.58 \times 10^{-4}$, $I = 0.1$, the concentration of $[HL^+]_T$ was varied from 2.58 to 12.92 mol dm⁻³. The results are given in Table 1. It is

Table 1. Values of $10^5 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s⁻¹) at different $[HL^+]$ and at different temperatures*

$[Rh^{III}]_T = 2.58 \times 10^{-4}$, $I = 0.1$ mol dm ⁻³ (NaClO ₄), pH = 4.3				
$10^3 [HL]$ mol dm ⁻³	45°	55°	60°	65°C
2.58	1.56 (1.54)	2.85 (2.75)	3.60 (3.54)	4.55 (4.53)
5.16	2.43 (2.45)	3.90 (4.27)	5.02 (5.42)	6.70 (6.88)
7.74	3.07 (3.05)	5.30 (5.24)	6.60 (6.59)	8.25 (8.32)
10.32	3.57 (3.48)	6.40 (5.91)	7.72 (7.39)	9.49 (9.29)
12.92	3.84 (3.80)	6.80 (6.41)	8.19 (7.97)	10.03 (9.99)
$10^4 k_{\text{an}}/s^{-1}$	0.60	0.96	1.16	1.43
K_M	134.2	155.3	170.1	180.0

*Data in the parenthesis are for k_{cald}

observed that as $[HL^+]_T$ increases, the k_{obs} value increases in a nonlinear fashion indicating thereby outer-sphere complexation between the reactant species. The reaction sequence given in Scheme 1 is consistent with the experimental data.

Scheme 1

The rate law for the anation reaction can be derived as follows :

$$\text{Rate} = k_{\text{an}} [\text{o.s.}]_e = k_{\text{an}} K_M [\text{RhOH}^{2+}]_e [\text{HL}]_e \quad (4)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 [\text{RhOH}^{2+}]_T &= [\text{RhOH}^{2+}]_e + [\text{o.s.}]_e \\
 &= [\text{RhOH}^{2+}]_e + K_M [\text{RhOH}^{2+}]_e [\text{HL}]_e \\
 &= [\text{RhOH}^{2+}]_e \{1 + K_M [\text{HL}]_e\}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$[\text{RhOH}^{2+}]_e = [\text{RhOH}^{2+}]_T / \{1 + K_M [\text{HL}]_e\} \quad (5)$$

Substituting the value of $[\text{RhOH}^{2+}]_e$ in eqn. (4),

$$\text{Rate} = k_{\text{an}} K_M [\text{RhOH}^{2+}]_T [\text{HL}]_e / \{1 + K_M [\text{HL}]_e\} \quad (6)$$

$$\text{Rate} = k_{\text{obs}} [\text{RhOH}^{2+}]_T \quad (7)$$

Eqn. (6) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned}
 k_{\text{obs}} &= k_{\text{an}} K_M [\text{HL}]_e / \{1 + K_M [\text{HL}]_e\} \\
 \text{or, } k_{\text{obs}}^{-1} &= k_{\text{an}}^{-1} + (k_{\text{an}} K_M)^{-1} [\text{HL}]^{-1}
 \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

The plot of k_{obs}^{-1} vs $[\text{HL}]^{-1}$ should be linear with an intercept = k_{an}^{-1} and slope = $(k_{\text{an}} K_M)^{-1}$. This plot was linear at all the experimental temperatures studied. k_{an} was determined from the reciprocal of the intercept and K_M calculated from intercept/slope ratio. The values of k_{an} , K_M are given in Table 1.

Effect of temperature on the rate : The reactions were studied at four different temperatures with different ligand concentrations. Activation parameters were calculated using Eyring equation and compared with literature data of the analogous systems (Table 2). The low ΔH^\ddagger value compared with the aqua-exchange process¹⁵ together with

Table 2. Activation parameters for analogous systems

System	ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	Ref.
$[\text{Rh}(\text{OH}_2)_5\text{OH}]^{2+}/\text{H}_2\text{O}$	103.0	–	15
Pyridine-2-aldoxime	87.5	–52.3	20
DL-Methionine	75.0	–81.3	6
L-Cysteine	72.6 ± 0.6	–91 ± 2	21
Adenosine	93.0 ± 5.5	–49 ± 16	22
Cytidine	62.7 ± 4.2	–129 ± 12	13
L-Aspartic acid	62.0 ± 1.2	–120.8 ± 3.4	4
Uridine	46.5 ± 1.4	–181 ± 4	23
Picolinic acid	35.46 ± 0.95	–214.7 ± 2.84	This work

highly negative ΔS^\ddagger value, suggests an associative mechanism. $k_{\text{an}}(25^\circ) = 2.34 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$, which is found to be greater than $10^8 k_{\text{ex}}(25^\circ) = 4.0$ (Ref.16) also supports the above proposition. The values of ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger are $35.46 \pm 0.95 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $-214.7 \pm 2.84 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$, respectively. ΔH^0 and ΔS^0 values were calculated from the $\ln K_M$ vs T^{-1} plot¹⁷ and the correlation coefficient was found to be 0.999. ΔH^0 was calculated from the slope and ΔS^0 from the intercept with $r = 0.999$. ΔH^0 and ΔS^0 values were found to be $13.36 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $82.75 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$, respectively. ΔG^0 value of the anation reaction was found to be $-11.3 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$. Negative ΔG^0 supports the spontaneous formation of an outer-sphere association complex.

Fig. 1. Absorbance spectra of $[\text{Rh}(\text{OH}_2)_5\text{OH}_2^{2+}]$, picolinic acid, and the mixture: (1) $[\text{Rh}(\text{OH}_2)_5\text{OH}_2^{2+}] = 2.58 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, at $\text{pH} = 4.3$, (2) $[\text{Picolinic acid}]_T = 12.92 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, at $\text{pH} = 4.3$, (3) $[\text{Rh}(\text{OH}_2)_5\text{OH}_2^{2+}] = 2.58 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{Picolinic acid}]_T = 12.92 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\text{pH} = 4.3$ at 65° at zero h, (4) $[\text{Rh}(\text{OH}_2)_5\text{OH}_2^{2+}] = 2.58 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{Picolinic acid}]_T = 12.92 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\text{pH} = 4.3$ at 65° after 15 min, (5) $[\text{Rh}(\text{OH}_2)_5\text{OH}_2^{2+}] = 2.58 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{Picolinic acid}]_T = 12.92 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\text{pH} = 4.3$ at 65° after 1 h, (6) $[\text{Rh}(\text{OH}_2)_5\text{OH}_2^{2+}] = 2.58 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{Picolinic acid}]_T = 12.92 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\text{pH} = 4.3$ at 65° after 3 h.

Experimental

The complex $[\text{Rh}(\text{OH}_2)_6(\text{ClO}_4)_3]$ was prepared according to the published method¹⁸. The complex was

characterized spectrally ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 396 \text{ nm}$, $\epsilon = 62$, $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 311 \text{ nm}$, $\epsilon = 67.4 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and by elemental analysis¹⁹.

The experimental condition was maintained to obtain the substrate complex $[\text{Rh}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5\text{OH}]^{2+}$ by adjusting pH of the solution to ≈ 4.3 where most of the hexaaquarhodium(III) gets converted into hydroxopentaaqua species. Above $\text{pH} 4.5$, precipitation of Rh^{III} occurred as reported earlier⁶.

The ligand picolinic acid may act as bidentate (O, N) donor. The product of the reaction between Rh^{III} complex and picolinic acid was prepared by mixing them in different mole ratios, viz. 1 : 2, 1 : 4, 1 : 8, and 1 : 10, and thermostating at 60° for 12 h. The absorption spectra exhibited the same λ_{max} (398 nm) with almost same absorbances. Upon addition of same acidic aquarhodium(III) solution to a solution of picolinic acid, an increase in absorbance in the visible range occurred. The absorption spectra of picolinic acid, Rh^{III} and mixture (Rh^{III} + picolinic acid) at the same pH, indicate the formation of an picolinic acid-rhodium(III) complex (Fig. 1). The absorbance increase of the mixture at different time intervals was observed. The ligand binds to Rh^{III} only through the carboxylate oxygen and through ring nitrogen. The composition of the complex formed, as determined by Job's method, was found to be 1 : 1 (metal : ligand). The pH of the solution was adjusted with $\text{NaOH}/\text{HClO}_4$ and the measurements were carried out on an Elico pH meter with an accuracy of ± 0.01 . Double-distilled water was used to prepare all the solutions. The other chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The absorbance measurements for kinetic studies were done using a Shimadzu UV-2101PC spectrophotometer. Reaction progress was monitored at 315 nm, pseudo-first order conditions were maintained throughout the runs by using a large (\geq ten-fold) excess of picolinic acid. The rate constants k_{obs} were obtained from the slopes of $\ln(A_\infty - A_t)$ vs t plots, of eqn., $\ln(A_\infty - A_t) = k_{\text{obs}} t + C$, where A_t and A_∞ are the absorbances of the reaction at the time t and at equilibrium, respectively. The reported rate data represented as an average of duplicate runs, were reproducible to within $\pm 3\%$. The correlation coefficient of plots used to determine k_{obs} were found to be 0.99 in most of the cases. There is a good agreement between the k_{obs} and k_{calc} values.

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